

"ASSESSING PRODUCTION AND MARKETING CONSTRAINTS IN POMEGRANATE CULTIVATION: A FARMER CENTRIC STUDY'S"¹Sunil Mahadev Lawate, ²A. A. Jambhale, Dr. Pallavi Lalasaheb Kolekar¹Department of Agricultural Economics, Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar
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Abstract

Pomegranate (Punica granatum) is a nutrient-rich fruit known for its juicy, ruby-red seeds and high antioxidant content. It grows in warm, arid climates, making it a valuable crop in Mediterranean and subtropical regions. The present investigation was undertaken in order to depict the "Economics of Production and Marketing of Pomegranate in Solapur District of Maharashtra." The fruit is indigenous to Iran and is widely grown throughout the Mediterranean region, including Iran, India, Spain, Egypt, China, and Barma.

The present study conducted in the Sangola and Mangalwedha two tehsils of Solapur district on the basis of maximum area under pomegranate cultivation. The purpose of present study was identifying constraints in production and marketing of pomegranate and suggest suitable measures. Three villages from each tehsil were selected randomly. Thus from six villages, 90 pomegranate growers were selected for present study. The primary data collected for the agriculture year 2023-24. Study revealed that the majority of the growers reported that major constraints were high cost of fertilizer and pesticides (61.42%), followed by lack of knowledge of recommended varieties (57.92%), lack of processing industry facilities (56.24%), High cost of seedlings (45.69%), Labour unavailability and high charges (44.79%), improper electricity availability (43.27%) and lack of loan facility (40.67%), etc. While it related to marketing, fluctuating market prices (57.94%), followed by shortage of quality antibiotics to produce export quality fruits (54.33%), payment insecurity (53.83%), lack of roads facilities for transportation (44.28%) and Lack of market information (39.61%), etc. These are the major constraints faced by sample growers in study area. With this framework in thoughts, the current study was conducted to find out the constraints encountered by the farmers and to suggest suitable recommendations to pomegranate growers.

Keywords: Pomegranate, production, marketing, constraints

Introduction:

Over the world Pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) are grown in tropical and subtropical climates. India is known as the World's Fruit and Vegetable Pocket. Pomegranate cultivation dates back thousands of years. The fruit is indigenous to Iran and is widely grown throughout the Mediterranean region, including Iran, Spain, Egypt, China, India and Barma. In India Maharashtra, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Gujarat and Tamil Nadu ranks subsequently.

India being the first in the production of pomegranate cultivation has approximately 234.57 ('000 ha') area under pomegranate with a production of 2933.85 ('000 MT) and productivity accounts 12.51 (MT/ha) respectively. In India pomegranate commercially grown in Maharashtra, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu hold ranks subsequently. At present Maharashtra is leading in pomegranate cultivation which accounts 115.67 ('000 ha') area, 1434.41 ('000 MT') production and 12.40 ('MT/ha') productivity respectively. (Source: Ministry of Agriculture & Farmer welfare, Govt. of India 2023-24).

Ganesh, Bhagwa, Sharad king, Ruby, Solapur Lal, Arakta and Mridula are the different varieties of pomegranate produced in Maharashtra. In Maharashtra pomegranate is commercially cultivated in Solapur, Ahmednagar, Nasik, Pune, Dhule, Sangli, Chatrapati Sambhaji nagar, Satara, Osmanabad and Latur districts of Maharashtra. During the recent decade Solapur, Ahmednagar and Nasik districts have attained a significant rank in respect of area under pomegranate production and quality of pomegranate.

Arrival pattern of pomegranate according to Bahar treatment.

1. June-July (Mrig bahar) coinciding with break of Monsoon.
2. February – March (Ambia bahar) and
3. September – October (Hasta bahar)

Pomegranate can be cultivated to produce fruit at any time of year, but usually only one bahar is taken from the orchard and the ideal fruiting

season depends on the availability of irrigation water and inputs. The end of May until August is the time you can harvest the Ambia Bahar fruits. The quality of fruits grown in the Mrig Bahar during the wet season is affected by bugs and diseases. October flowering fruits (Hasta bahar) are available in the market from March to May, when the supply of other fruits is reduced. Although pomegranate have very high demand during this period, growers get higher prices for their produce. (Auti, 2017)

Materials and Methods:

The present investigation has been undertaken in Solapur district of Maharashtra. Two tehsils viz. Sangola and Mangalwedha were selected purposively on the basis of maximum area under pomegranate cultivation. Pomegranate was the main fruit crop grown by this area, hence it was chosen for the present study because pomegranate crop was highly profitable as compared to other fruit crops. Three villages from each tehsil were selected randomly. Thus from six villages, 90 pomegranate farmers were selected for present study.

The primary data collected for the agriculture year 2023-24 were analyzed by using simple tabular approach and functional analysis method.

Total Sample size:

Source: Compile by author

Analytical Tools:

In the quantification of constraints expressed by the growers, Garrett's ranking method was used. The orders of merit given by the respondents was converted into rank by using the formula. To find out the most significant factor which influences the respondent, Garrett's ranking technique was used. As per this method, respondents asked to assign the rank for all factors and the outcomes of such ranking have been converted into score value with the help of the following formula,

Figure -1 Sampling Design:

Per cent position= $100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_j$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i th variable by j th respondents ($i = 1, 2, 3 \dots 10$)

N_j = No. of variables ranked by j th respondents ($j = 1, 2, 3 \dots 10$)

Results and Discussion:**Constraints faced by Pomegranate growers:**

The Pomegranate is more sensitive to susceptible to weather, fruit cracking and pest diseases. It also requires proper operation like preparatory tillage, weeding, spraying, application of proper fertilizer

and manure etc., for better productivity. At the time of survey, questions were asked to the sample farmers to understand the problem faced by them in production and marketing of pomegranate. Thus collected information was analyzed using Garret Ranking technique.

Constraints faced by Pomegranate growers in production:

Table 1 Per cent position and Garret value for problems in production of Pomegranate

Table 2 Preference for problems faced by growers in Pomegranate production

Sr. No.	$100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_j$	Percent position	Garret Value
1	$100*(1-0.5)/7$	7.14	78
2	$100*(2-0.5)/7$	21.43	66
3	$100*(3-0.5)/7$	35.71	57
4	$100*(4-0.5)/7$	50.00	50
5	$100*(5-0.5)/7$	64.29	43
6	$100*(6-0.5)/7$	78.57	35
7	$100*(7-0.5)/7$	92.86	21

The information regarding problems in production are presented in Table 1. The problem as labour unavailability and high charges was

Garret value is calculated by using the Garret ranking conversion table. In Table 1. Percent position was given along with Garret score the

Sr. No.	$100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_j$	Percent position	Garret Value
1	$100*(1-0.5)/5$	10	75
2	$100*(2-0.5)/5$	30	60
3	$100*(3-0.5)/5$	50	50
4	$100*(4-0.5)/5$	70	40
5	$100*(5-0.5)/5$	90	25

ranked as first by 26 respondents, second rank by 29 respondents, while nine respondents of them mentioned as last rank.

Similarly, high cost of pesticide and fertilizer ranked as first by 9 respondent, second ranked by 5 respondents 16 of them mentioned as last rank.

nearest value of per cent position was seen from the table and garret score was given to that per cent position. The high cost of pesticide and fertilizer got the first rank, followed by lack of knowledge about recommended varieties, lack of processing industries, high cost of seedlings, labour unavailability and high charges, improper electricity availability and lack of market information were ranked subsequently

Table 3 Garret score and rank of problems faced by Pomegranate growers

Sr. No	Constraints	Rank given by the respondent						
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
1.	Labour unavailability and high charges	26	29	17	7	1	1	9
2	Lack of knowledge about recommended varieties	18	28	17	6	6	10	4
3	Lack of processing industry facilities	15	11	29	18	11	1	5
4	High cost of pesticides, fertilizers	9	5	11	17	14	19	16
5	Improper electricity availability	5	4	11	20	21	17	12
6	Lack of credit facilities	8	6	0	12	27	24	13
7	High cost of seedlings	9	7	5	10	10	18	31

Table 4 Percent position and Garret value for problems in marketing of Pomegranate Constraints faced by Pomegranate growers in Marketing:

Sr. No	Constraints	Garret Score								%	Rank
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	Total		
1	High cost of pesticides, fertilizers	2028	1914	969	350	43	35	189	5528	61.42	I
2	Lack of knowledge about recommended varieties	1404	1848	969	300	258	350	84	5213	57.92	II
3	Lack of processing industry facilities	1170	726	1653	900	473	35	105	5062	56.24	III
4	High cost of seedlings	702	330	627	850	602	665	336	4112	45.69	IV
5	Labour unavailability and high charges	390	264	627	1000	903	595	252	4031	44.79	V
6	Improper electricity availability	624	396	554	600	1161	840	273	3894	43.27	VI
7	Lack of credit facilities	702	462	285	500	430	630	651	3660	40.67	VII

It is always expected that marketing system must be efficient to provide necessary environment for greater agriculture production through price incentive to producer at one hand and supply of quality products at one hand and supply of quality products at fair prices to the consumer on the other here an attempt has been made to study the problems faced by pomegranate growers in marketing of pomegranate.

The problem faced by farmers during marketing of pomegranate are mentioned in Table 4 and it reveals that, out of 90 pomegranate

farmers, price fluctuation in market for pomegranate was ranked first by 28 respondents, second rank by 26 respondents, while, 7 respondents has mentioned as last rank. Similarly, shortage of high quality antibiotics to produce export quality fruits rank first by 26 respondents, second ranked by 19 respondents and 12 of them mentioned as last rank and lack of market information ranked first by 6, second by 5 and last by 35 respondent respectively.

Table 5 Preference for problems faced by farmers in Pomegranate marketing

Sr. No	Constraints	Rank given by the respondent				
		I	II	III	IV	V
1	Shortage of quality antibiotics to produce export quality fruits	26	19	18	15	12
2	Price fluctuation in market	28	26	18	9	7
3	Payment insecurity	21	24	20	12	14
4	Lack of road facility for transportation	9	14	16	28	22
5	Lack of market information	6	5	18	26	35

Table 6 Garret score and ranking of problems faced by Pomegranate farmers

Sr. No	Constraints	Garret Score						%	Rank
		I	II	III	IV	V	Total		
1	Shortage of quality antibiotics to produce export quality fruits	1950	1140	900	600	300	4890	54.33	II
2	Price fluctuation in market	2100	1680	900	360	175	5215	57.94	I
3	Payment insecurity	1575	1440	1000	480	350	4845	53.83	III
4	Lack of road facility for transportation	675	840	800	1120	550	3985	44.28	IV
5	Lack of market information	450	300	900	1040	875	3565	39.61	V

The problem of Price fluctuation in market got the first rank, followed by shortage of quality antibiotics to produce export quality fruits, payment insecurity, lack of road facility for transportation and lack of efficient market information got II, III, IV and V rank respectively.

Conclusion:

In concern with pomegranate production problems were reported by sample growers in research area was high cost of fertilizer and pesticides (61.42%), followed by lack of knowledge of recommended varieties (57.92%), lack of processing industry facilities (56.24%), High cost of seedlings (45.69%), Labour unavailability and high charges (44.79%), improper electricity availability (43.27%) and lack of loan facility (40.67%), etc.

While it related to marketing, fluctuating market prices (57.94%), followed by shortage of quality antibiotics to produce export quality fruits (54.33%), payment insecurity (53.83%), lack of roads facilities for transportation (44.28%) and Lack of market information (39.61%), etc. These are the major problems faced by sample growers in study area.

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